

Title	Proposed TNA pilots for innovators in technology
Work package n°	6
Deliverable n°	6.3
Lead beneficiary	CNRS
Author(s)	L. Rivier, (CNRS/CEA), O. Laurent (CEA), S. Sauvage (IMT), R. Petracca (CNR), A. Dubost (CNRS)
Deliverable Type	Report
Dissemination Level	PU
Estimated delivery date	November 2024
Actual delivery date	March 2026
Version	V4
Reviewed by	S. Philippin (CNRS), J. Wenger (UCC)
Accepted by	
Comments	V1 Submitted May 2024 V2 Submitted Jul 2024 V3 Draft submitted Mar 2025 finalised Jul 2025 V4 Submitted Mar 2026 after EC's review

Table of Content

<i>Introduction</i>	3
<i>Assessment and analysis of private sector access in ATMO-ACCESS</i>	3
Access statistics to ATMO-ACCESS from the private sector	4
Private sector user feedback and recommendations to improve/increase access	6
Strategy to attract more private users towards Atmospheric RIs	9
<i>Presentation of a new TNA pilot for innovators in technology: the Atmobox</i>	13
Description of the services	13
Description of the central facilities involved	18
<i>Conclusion and next steps</i>	19
<i>Annex 1: Summary of private sector access</i>	21
<i>Annex 2: Description of the instrument tests performed at the ATC Metrology Laboratory</i>	22

Introduction

This document is a report on Task 6.3 titled “New access modalities for innovators in technology”. The goal of this task is to develop synergy and enhance innovation services especially for users in the private sector. The key research areas identified include the development and testing of instruments, sensor technologies, calibrations and benchmarking through metrology.

Assessment and analysis of private sector access in ATMO-ACCESS

The description of the application, review and selection process for Trans National Access TNA to ATMO-ACCESS facilities is provided in the project document [Milestone 9.1](#). The specific process for private sector users is accessible here: [Trans-National Access for Private Sector – ATMO-ACCESS](#). Applications from private sector users follow a similar workflow to other applications, except that a review is conducted as quickly as possible. This differs from the regular calls where selection of successful applications is made in a meeting scheduled after the call has closed. While engagement of private sector users in atmospheric RIs remains inherently challenging, the call for private sector access is continuously open to allow more flexibility. Users can submit their proposals without following any specific call schedule. To address these challenges, continuous and targeted communication efforts were implemented throughout the project. These included direct engagement with industrial stakeholders via partner networks, and bilateral exchanges to better understand user needs and facilitate access to RI services.

Application

Once a call is identified the first major task for the user is to fill in the application form with information on: name, nationality, home institution of the users; a description of the work to be performed during the access; dissemination plans; description of users’ estimated travel & subsistence costs.

The application form is integrated and submitted via PASS, the access management platform of the project. The user is encouraged to contact the TNA provider before finalizing their application. Once submitted, the eligibility and feasibility (confirmed by TNA provider) are assessed before being reviewed. For private sector users, the following aspects are given high weighting in the review process, innovation potential of the TNA activity, technological developments, market relevance and impact on the economy.

The private sector call benefits from a shortened evaluation process. Proposals are processed as they arrive, with an independent review conducted as rapidly as possible (foreseen decision time: ~2-3 weeks).

Post access requirements

The user and access provider are required to return the following:

- Confirmation of Access signed by the TNA Provider within 2 weeks after the access.
- Attestation of the TNA activity within a maximum of 8 weeks. Depending on the type of service, this could be an activity report, calibration document or training certificate.
- User feedback questionnaire within 3 weeks of the access to enable evaluation of TNA operations and recommend improvements as appropriate.
- Information on results of the activity, e.g. data and scientific publications. Private sector users can request to be exempt from providing results and data that may be related to intellectual property.
- Carbon footprint assessment of the TNA activity.

Access statistics to ATMO-ACCESS from the private sector

In total, 46 TNA activities involving private sector users were supported during ATMO-ACCESS. 42 of these activities have been completed (see annex 1), 2 projects were cancelled, 2 reports are being finalised. The activities were performed by SMEs and led by expert scientists 90% of the time (the rest being led by Engineers, technician or post-doc). The private sector users were from 14 different countries and took place in 14 countries (see table 1 below). Nine countries (Austria, France, Germany, Greece, Finland, Italy, The Netherlands, UK and Switzerland) are both countries of origin and destination of private sector users.

The main field of activity for private sector users was the atmospheric domain in Earth and Environmental science (85%), with the remainder being from engineering technology, eco-biosphere and chemistry). Notably, 67% of the applicants were new users. The type of services requested were Research/innovation (70%), technical (28%) and training services (2%).

Origin of private sector users	Countries where private sector TNA took place
Austria	France (ACMCC SIRTAs: CL)
Belgium	Switzerland (PACS-C2: ASC)
Finland	Cyprus (CAO: OBS) France (SIRTAs: OBS) UK (MAC: ASC)

France	Cyprus (USRL: MOB) Germany (WCCAP: CL) Spain (ISAF IZO: OBS + AGORA: OBS) Poland (WOS: OBS + AMP: MOB)
Germany	Austria (SBO: OBS) Finland (PAL-SOB: OBS) Italy (CIAO: OBS) Netherlands (CESAR: OBS) Poland (WOS: OBS)
Greece	Cyprus (USRL: MOB) Romania (RADO: OBS) Poland (AMP: MOB)
Italy	Germany (WCCAP: CL) Greece (ATMOS: OBS)
Latvia / Lithuania	Poland (WOS: OBS)
Slovenia	Finland (SMEAR II: OBS) France (SIRTA: OBS) Germany (WCCAP: CL) Greece (ATMOS: OBS) Spain (EUPHORE: ASC) Spain (BCN: OBS)
Sweden	France (ICOS ATC: CL)
Switzerland	France (SIRTA: OBS) Germany (QUAREC: ASC) Greece (ATMOS: OBS)
The Netherlands	France (COPDD: OBS) Greece (ATMOS: OBS + PANGEA: OBS). Ireland (IASC: ASC) Poland (WOPAS: OBS) Spain (BCN: OBS)
UK	Finland (PAL-SOD: OBS) Italy (CMV-PT: OBS) The Netherlands (CESAR: OBS)
USA	France (COPDD: OBS) Poland (WOS: OBS)

Table 1: Countries of origin and destination of private sector users in the ATMO ACCESS project, with the accessed facilities in brackets. OBS is for observational site; MOB stands for mobile platform laboratory; CL for central laboratory and ASC for atmospheric simulation chamber.

Most TNA activities were carried out at observational sites (35), six took place at central laboratories, six in atmospheric simulation chambers and four at mobile platform laboratories. Some projects used a combination of facility types (for ex: observatory platform and mobile facility, observatory platform and central laboratories). Three types of access were provided,

with physical access (hands-on access of user at facility) and a combination of physical and remote access roughly equal in popularity, Figure 1.

Figure 1: Type of access requested by private sector users within ATMO-ACCESS.

Overall, the programme supported 42 completed TA projects involving private sector users, representing approximately 13% of total users. This level of participation is particularly significant in the atmospheric research domain, where industrial uptake has historically been limited, and constitutes one of the highest engagement levels observed to date.

Private sector user feedback and recommendations to improve/increase access

User feedback was acquired directly via systematic distribution of user feedback questionnaires, supported by reminders and follow-ups. In total, 161 feedback forms were collected out of 297 completed TNA projects, corresponding to a response rate of 54%, increasing to 59% among private sector users. This response rate reflects a commonly observed challenge when engaging users, and in particular private sector users, who often face time constraints and have limited incentives to provide formalised feedback, rather than a lack of effort in collecting user input. In addition, qualitative feedback was gathered through direct interactions with users during and after access provision. Overall, users reported a high degree of satisfaction with the ATMO-ACCESS services, as reflected in the average rating of 4.4 out of 5 marks. Further details can be found in [Deliverable 6.5](#).

The feedback received can be split in two categories:

Very positive points:

- Practical information provided on how to apply (documentation, FAQs, etc.)
- Interaction with and support by the TNA Team
- Duration of the selection process
- Scientific and technical support to conduct research and interpret the results
- Technical support for instruments, e.g. calibrations
- Logistic support at the facility (space, computing, libraries, accommodation)
- Overall appreciation of the services accessed and their flexibility

The private sector user appreciated the closer relations between the company and the research facility, emphasizing the very effective sharing of competence¹. Importantly, 72% of respondents indicated that their TNA activities would not have been possible without financial support for travel and subsistence.

Points for improvement:

- Publicity and information about the access, building on the communication efforts already implemented, which should be further strengthened, structured and made more visible towards the private sector.
- Length, information required and easiness of the application form
- The quantity of post access work was too much
- Support for organizing the access was sometimes lacking
- Administrative support (including the reimbursement of travel & subsistence expenses)

The following section lists several recommendations for improving and increasing private sector access to the research infrastructures. It is compiled from direct interaction with the private sector either during meetings or bilateral exchanges. The recommendations were partially applied during the project but serve as a guideline for future projects involving access to environmental research infrastructures.

1. Improve and further structure the communication of the RI access opportunities towards the private sector through the following: increased participation in exhibitions/fairs dedicated to measurement technologies; strengthened communications with National Metrology Institutes (Euramet); organisation of open house events offered by access providers; development of dedicated and targeted mailing lists.
2. Reimbursement process is still complicated. Advancing the funds is sometimes a problem. A simplification based on a fixed rate for accommodation and subsistence,

¹ Notable is the access provided to a spin-off company from the University of Namur that enabled the improvements to the efficiency of a catalyst that is already under patent.

- combined with reimbursement of transport costs could be envisaged. The access provider could advance some of the expenses.
3. Continuously ongoing call (open ended) is viewed as a good thing. It allows flexibility that is appreciated by users from the private sector.
 4. The carbon footprint assessment should not be a burden on the user.
 5. Need for a simple legal framework including confidentiality, insurance that would be prepared with the private sector.
 6. The transnational aspect of the access is sometimes perceived as limiting, due to language barriers and geographical distance, as private sector users, particularly SMEs, often prefer solutions located closer to their place of operation, which may affect their willingness to engage in transnational access.
 7. The inter RI access is not effective even though no request was made so far.
 8. For repeated access, the application process could be simplified.

In terms of the research topics that could be further developed through TNA, a private sector survey gave the following results:

1. Testing new aerosol lidars.
2. Isotope intercalibration project with instrument manufacturers.
3. Organic species produced in chamber experiments: detection and calibration with advanced Mass Spectrometry techniques.
4. New types of atmospheric measurements, e.g. oxidative potential of particles, bioaerosols, ions.
5. Focus on mobile platforms.
6. Atmospheric processing of volatile organic compounds.
7. Miniature and low-cost sensors.
8. Quality assurance and quality control procedures, characterisation of instruments.
9. Telecommunication, transmission of data via satellite, big data.
10. Numerical modelling.

Some of these topics could be addressed through services offered within the Virtual Access Portal of ATMO-ACCESS. Considering low-cost sensors and instrument characterisation, a new type of service was developed and is described in the following section.

Table 2 summarizes potential key performance indicators (KPIs) to be considered in future projects offering access to RIs in the environmental domain.

Category	KPI Metric	Potential target
Geographic Reach	Origin of private sector users	15 countries
Industrial user demand	Number of access requests from private sector	15% of total access requests
	Number of companies engaged	Number of companies (depending on project scope and potential user base)
Outreach	Number of industrial success stories	5 videos / stories released during the project
Efficiency	Average time from initial access request to access start	4-6 weeks
User satisfaction	Rating of the overall access process	Average rating >4.2 out of 5

Table 2: Suggested KPIs to measure private sector engagement in access programmes to Environmental RIs

Strategy to attract more private users towards Atmospheric RIs

The proportion of private sector TNA in ATMO-ACCESS was 13%. Some strategies were implemented in ATMO- ACCESS to attract the private sector, such as the creation of [success stories](#) from previous users (see work from the WP2 dedicated to communications).

This section describes further actions that could be implemented to increase attractiveness of atmospheric RIs to the private sector. They include some concrete and short-term actions, as well as some aspects that require more strategic planning.

Technical solutions to better attract the private sector

- **Create an "Industry" Menu Tab:** Add a dedicated section for private sector (industry) users within the RI websites, providing easy access to services offered, TNA opportunities, training and case studies.
- **Design Service/Access Landing Pages:** Develop landing pages tailored to private sector users, highlighting services, tools, and benefits specific to industry applications. Incorporate intuitive navigation and detailed service descriptions.

- **Augment the ENVRI Catalogue²:** Add services specifically targeting the private sector to the ENVRI catalogue for increased exposure.
- Implement a **Quality Charter for Access**, ensuring transparency and reliability in industrial collaborations.
- Expand **remote access and virtual platforms** to enable industry engagement without physical constraints.

Develop targeted expert services

- **Leverage RI Expert Knowledge:** Build a portfolio of expert consulting services tailored to private sector needs, offering actionable insights into environmental monitoring, sustainability, and compliance.
- **Dedicated Training Programs:** Develop training modules and workshops for industry professionals on advanced technologies, environmental data interpretation, and regulatory compliance.

Communication and Outreach

Effective communication is essential for raising awareness of RI capabilities:

- **Industry-Focused Newsletter:** Publish a quarterly newsletter featuring success stories, services, upcoming events and training opportunities tailored to the private sector.
- **Market Analysis:** Perform detailed market segmentation to identify and target specific industrial sectors most likely to benefit from RI services.
- **Showcase Success Stories:** Actively promote examples of successful collaborations between RIs and industry, demonstrating tangible value. Share these through newsletters, webinars, and social media campaigns.
- **Feedback Mechanisms:** Implement robust feedback systems to continuously refine and improve services based on industry user input.
- **Cost-Effective Solutions:** Highlight how RI services can reduce costs, improve efficiency, and ensure compliance with environmental regulations.

Develop strategic partnership

- **Synergies with ENVRI:** Strengthen partnerships with the ENVRI community to leverage shared expertise and broaden outreach to industry stakeholders.
- **Innovation and Industry Support Hub:** Establish a centralized hub for innovation services, streamlining communication and support for private sector users, including

² <https://innovation.envri.eu/innovation-services/>

pricing models and intellectual property rights as outlined in the current ENVRINNOV EU project³.

- **Collaborative Projects:** Actively seek partnerships with industry for joint research and innovation projects that align with both environmental and business goals. Explore opportunities in the EU Horizon programs.
- Create **Industry Advisory Boards** in RIs, composed of experts from relevant industrial sectors to provide strategic guidance.
- **Integrate into Strategic Plans:** Explicitly include private sector engagement in the strategic agendas of RIs, systematically including socio-economic impact as an integral component.
- **Dedicated Liaison Personnel:** Appoint industry liaison officers to serve as the primary point of contact, facilitating communication and understanding between RIs and private companies. These personnel could facilitate the following:
 - Embed private sector collaborations.
 - Encourage the development of **customized services for industry**, including feasibility studies, prototyping, and testing services.
 - Strengthen **intellectual property management** by creating structured licensing frameworks to encourage commercialization.
- **Sustainability Frameworks:** Align RI services with corporate sustainability goals, including ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) metrics.
- **Innovation Platforms:** Create platforms for co-developing innovative technologies and solutions that address emerging environmental challenges.

Much of the above strategy was carried out by the European funded project ENVRINNOV, that delivered a common Innovation Roadmap for the ENVRI community to enhance technologies and services. Lasting until the end of 2026, it aims to co-design, test, and validate strategies for innovation collaboration between ENVRI, industry, and the scientific community. The project supports the establishment of an ENVRI Innovation Hub (EIH) with tools, policies, digital platforms, and capacity-building programmes gathering several of the points listed above in the strategy section.

The recommendation made in the strategy above to establish visible “Industry” or “Innovation” sections on RI websites, and publishing service-level agreements and IP policy guidelines, and developing annual innovation strategies within ENVRINNOV, signals an institutional shift toward clearer value propositions for private stakeholders.

³ <https://envri.eu/envrinnov/>

The emphasis on success stories, market analysis, and targeted communication channels further strengthens the positioning of ENVRI as accessible and business-relevant partners (see strategy section above).

The proposed methodology in ENVRINNOV for regularly updating an extended e-catalogue - based on stakeholder feedback, standardized service templates, analytics, and benchmarking - introduces a dynamic governance model that mirrors private-sector expectations regarding transparency, responsiveness, and service reliability.

To better engage with the private sector, a first step in ENVRINNOV involved a comprehensive analysis of existing ENVRI services and technological gaps, which informs the identification of service areas where private users - such as environmental technology developers, SMEs, and consultancy firms - can derive practical value and contribute to co-creation processes.

A key element aimed at supporting industry uptake is the ENVRI Innovation Resources Toolbox. It is being developed as an open-access, modular digital platform within the ENVRI-Hub to support and guide innovation activities for both ENVRI members and external partners, including private sector users. It offers a structured suite of guidelines, templates, best practices and practical tools that accompany the typical stages of the innovation lifecycle - from initial idea generation and collaboration setup, through technology development, to technology transfer and commercialization. The Toolbox contains resources such as collaboration checklists and canvases to help frame partnerships, lists of networking platforms and funding opportunities relevant to innovation, and ready-to-use templates for confidentiality agreements, memoranda of understanding, and data or material transfer agreements, all designed to lower the transactional barriers for engaging with research infrastructures. It also integrates tools for assessing Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) and case studies from within the ENVRI community to illustrate successful innovation and partnership pathways. In addition, sections on technology transfer and intellectual property management provide web resources, guidelines and basic introductions to commercialization strategies that can be directly useful for companies and SMEs considering collaboration with ENVRI research infrastructures. The Toolbox is being co-designed and iteratively refined with input from the wider ENVRI community and tested in live settings, ensuring it addresses real-world needs and can cater to users unfamiliar with traditional RI frameworks, thereby enhancing accessibility and relevance for private innovators.

Moreover, ENVRINNOV places significant emphasis on capacity building tailored to fostering private sector engagement (Dedicated Training programs in the strategy above). Survey results collected reveal strong interest among participating organisations in training on innovation

management, technology transfer, and industry collaboration, underscoring the importance of equipping both RI personnel and potential private partners with the competencies needed to establish effective cooperative frameworks.

The establishment of a digital platform and an Innovation Hub governance and business model is intended to provide a sustainable interface where private users can discover services, identify collaboration opportunities, and track innovation support offerings. Through these concrete activities—strategic analysis, pilot testing of collaboration models, resource development, targeted training, and platform design—ENVRINNOV is systematically shaping the ENVRI landscape to be more attractive and accessible to private users seeking engagement with environmental research infrastructures.

Presentation of a new TNA pilot for innovators in technology: the Atmobox

This section describes a new service enabling two modes of access to a new form of atmospheric sensing technology called the Atmobox:

1. Testing sensor elements against reference instruments.
2. Use of the modular Atmobox to simultaneously measure Greenhouse Gases (GHG) and air quality parameters on a campaign basis.

The first mode of access to the Atmobox is especially suited for the private sector where companies developing new sensors can benchmark them with established procedures against reference instrumentation. This new service is inter-RI and is supported by the ATC (Atmosphere Thematic Centre) in ICOS and the CiGas-IMT Nord Europe (Centre of Reactive Trace Gases In-Situ Measurements) in ACTRIS.

The service was made available to users in March 2024 via the [Private sector call](#) and the [last general call for access](#). One TNA proposal requested access but could not be realised in the end. The Atmobox was sent to EMPA (Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology) in the frame of the [Hybrid school on sensors and drones](#).

Description of the services

SERVICE 1 - Testing sensor elements against reference instruments

TYPE OF SERVICE	Research and Technical service
------------------------	--------------------------------

SERVICE DESCRIPTION

The Atmobox provides a modular platform to integrate mid and low-cost sensor elements allowing benchmarking and performance assessment including comparison with reference instruments. The platform can incorporate up to 8 sensors mounted at once in 1 or 2 “exposure cells”. The cells are designed for reactive and non-reactive gas and allow sensors to be exposed to gas with monitored and controlled environmental parameters (pressure, temperature and relative humidity).

The Atmobox has a versatile datalogger with automatic data transfer (4G or Wifi) to a FTP/SFTP server. Sensors require an interfaced electronic board to integrate the Atmobox system. The board handles the power supply and the interface with the versatile data logger. Standard analog output sensors may use a generic interface board whereas specific digital output sensors may require a specific one. Several interface boards are currently available for different brands/models.

The service includes:

- Administrative support to comply with internal procedures for accessing facilities (physical).
- Administrative and technical support for providing a workspace for visitors during physical access.
- Administrative support and advice for transportation and storage of equipment.
- Technical support to fulfil visitor needs and constraints related to installation, deployment and operation of equipment: power connections, remote access, storage, security constraints, internet.
- Testing/intercomparisons of sensor elements.
- Sensor characterization under controlled conditions according to “standard” procedures.
- Scientific support for supervision and analysis of collected data.

ATMOSPHERE TYPE	Ambient, partially controlled (e.g. targeted gas). Monitored and/or controlled environmental parameters are pressure, temperature and relative humidity.
TYPE OF ACCESS	Physical and Remote access or a combination of both.
TARGET USERS	Private sector and innovators of technology in other sectors.

SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered in 2024 for GHG, in 2025 for other parameters)
AVAILABILITY PERIOD	All year round
TIME CONSTRAINTS	None
CONTACT	Leonard Rivier, Olivier Laurent, Stéphane Sauvage
SERVICE 2 -Access to Atmobox as a transportable resource	
TYPE OF SERVICE	Research service
SERVICE DESCRIPTION	<p>The Atmobox (see description above under Service 1) can be deployed in the field on a campaign basis mode.</p> <p>The Atmobox allows for up to 8 sensors to be mounted at once. Potential atmospheric concentration to be measured are CO₂, CH₄, CO, NO₂, O₃, VOCs, NH₃, Particulate Matter (PM).</p> <p>It has a versatile datalogger at 1 Hz for atmospheric compounds (see above), GPS position and meteorological parameters, with an automatic data transfer (4G, Wifi) and remote control.</p> <p>It allows concomitant measurement of both GHG gases and air quality related gases.</p> <p>It allows automatic quality control and calibration in field (depending on the atmospheric species). The Atmobox includes target gases to automatically perform regular quality controls.</p> <p>The service includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Shipment of the Atmobox to the user.- Remote scientific and technical support for installation.- Remote scientific and technical support for operation.- Training
CONTACT	Leonard Rivier, Olivier Laurent, Stéphane Sauvage
ATMOSPHERE TYPE	Ambient
TYPE OF ACCESS	Physical to a mobile platform
TARGET USERS	Researchers
SERVICE STATUS	The service is available (operational and ready to be offered from 2024 for CO ₂ , from 2025 onwards for other compounds)

AVAILABILITY PERIOD	All year round
TIME CONSTRAINTS	Max duration of a campaign is three months

Testing sensors against reference instruments:

Sensible elements

Reference instrument

Atmo box

Figure 2: the Atmobox design

Figure 3: Atmo Box and reference instrument side by side

Figure 4: Demonstration test bed: example of deployed Atmoboxes

Deployment on top of the LSCE (Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement) building in Saclay near Paris, for comparison with reference instruments. Figure 5 shows double casing which includes target gases for automatic quality control.

Figure 5: Double casing system for the deployment of the Atmobox on top of LSCE building

Description of the central facilities involved

Figure 6: The ATC Metrology Lab in ICOS

The main tasks of the ATC Metrology Laboratory are:

- Testing of instruments for measuring greenhouse gases (GHG), producing a test report and a certificate of compliance. Development of meaningful tests (see annex 2 for a detailed description of the tests).
- Elaborating the measurement/calibration protocols.
- Investigating possible artifacts with the sampling system or analysers.
- Monitoring developments in atmospheric measurement technologies.
- Providing network support and [spare instruments](#) when necessary.
- Development of new sensors through R&D programs at national and international level.
- Participating at the European training centre for ICOS atmospheric measurements with the Data Unit.

CiGAS IMT:

From the start of 2025, Atmoboxes were also available at CiGAS, the European Topical Centre for Reactive Trace Gases In-Situ Measurements. The key-mission of CiGas is to offer current state-of-the art operational support to ACTRIS National Facilities (NFs), operational and exploratory platforms, which are operating instrumentation for continuous long-term measurements of volatile organic compounds (VOCs), condensable vapours and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) as well as ammonia (NH₃) in the atmosphere. That includes activities to guide research and service development in the field of reactive trace gases and to develop towards future user needs, utilizing innovative methodologies. The operational support to ACTRIS NFs is supplemented by tailored services for users from the Global Atmospheric Watch Network (GAW) and other atmospheric observation networks, academia, business, industry, and public

services depending on the respective resources. CiGas is composed of 6 units sharing expertise and related activities.

Figure 7: the CiGAS laboratory.

CiGas operates and supports instrumentation and observations for the in-situ measurement of reactive trace gases. The core activities of CiGas are to ensure sustainable and traceable high-quality data and data products of in-situ measured atmospheric reactive trace gases with known uncertainty. These include:

- Development, testing and implementing advanced measurement technologies and data evaluation algorithms
- Testing prototypes of gas analytical devices
- Auditing measurement sites, and consultancy
- Performing intercomparison (round robin or side-by-side)
- enhancing the competence of the operative personnel by training.

More detail can be found on the website: <https://www.actris.eu/topical-centre/cigas>.

Conclusion and next steps

To date, private sector access represents approximately 13% of all access activities in the project. This represents a strong level of engagement in the atmospheric research domain, where participation from industry has traditionally been limited. The access activities take place across European countries (and not within a single country) stimulating international collaboration, in line with the philosophy of TNA activities.

Through these unique access opportunities, the private sector benefits from the scientific credibility of the RIs and an association can also have added market value in the private sector in terms of visibility and recognition. RIs are encouraged to further leverage this aspect, as it can help attract more private sector users.

The private sector appreciates the flexibility in working with RIs. The co-design of access activities can lead to very efficient results, and the private users specifically highlight the benefits of gaining access to the technical and scientific expertise available at the facilities and within the RIs as a whole.

The Atmobox pilot developed during the project will be improved by enhancing the air quality measurement capabilities, making it more accessible to users from the private sector, as well as to academic researchers and public authorities.

Recommendations to improve and increase access for the private sector include measures to reduce the administrative burden, improve communication, and create simple legal frameworks addressing confidentiality and intellectual property rights. A more tailored service offer, focusing on services that are more mature in the RIs, rather than the full catalogue, may prove more attractive to the private sector and easier to promote. It is also recommended that an industry liaison function is established within RIs to communicate directly with private sector users, support the development of collaborative relationships, and help deliver services that are best suited to their needs.

To further build on these results and address the areas identified for improvement, a more structured approach to private sector engagement is proposed. In the short term, communication and outreach activities will be further consolidated and targeted towards relevant industrial sectors, building on existing networks and ongoing interactions. In parallel, efforts will continue to simplify access procedures and promote tailored service offers. In the medium term, more structured engagement mechanisms may be developed, including the continuation and further targeting of the open call for private sector users, stronger support through industry liaison functions, and wider deployment of demonstrators such as the Atmobox. Progress has been monitored through a limited set of indicators, including the share of private sector users in TNA activities, the number of applications received from industry, the proportion of successful applications, and user satisfaction where feedback was available. Recurrent users and follow-up collaborations also provide useful indications of sustained engagement. These indicators will continue to be used and further refined to support future monitoring.

Annex 1: Summary of private sector access

#	ATMO CALL	Status	Institution Name	Institution status	Institution Country	Lead user profile	Field of activity	New user?	Type of services requested	Facility	Type of access	Title & Acronym of the project
1	ATMO 1st TNA call	Complete	schubert GmbH	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Germany	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and env	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for FMI PAL-SOL, FI (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	Source appointment of Arctic carboxonous aerosol using the Angstrom exponent (LAPPOSS)
2	ATMO 1st TNA call	Complete	Aerrod d.o.o.	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Slovenia	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and env	No	Technical services	WCCAP_DE (CJ)	Physical access (hand)	Intercomparison of optical absorption measurements using newly developed portable Aerosolometer AE43 and Authentication prototype with extended wavelength range (Inter AE)
3	ATMO 1st TNA call	Complete	Karisa Oy	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	FINLAND	Engineer, Techn	ENV-ATMO - Earth and env	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for CAO, CY (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	Thermo Desorption - Multi-chrome chemical Oxidation inlet -Mass Spectrometry (TO-MHOMAS) for atmospheric aerosol precursor and security research - proof of concept
4	ATMO 1st TNA call	Complete	Aerrod d.o.o.	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Slovenia	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and env	No	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for SMEAR-II, FI (DBS), LUPHORE, ES (ASQ)		Combination of Physic	Advanced carboxonous aerosol appointment using Total Carbon Analyser and newly developed Aerosolometer prototype with extended wavelength range (ACAA-TC-BC 9)
5	ATMO 1st TNA call	Complete	Terra Modus Consultants Limited	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	United Kingdom	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and env	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for OAN-PV, IT (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	Midsize Enhanced Volatile Organic Compounds (MEVOC)
6	ATMO 2nd TNA call	Complete	Yatasa Oy	Other industrial and/or profit private organization	Finland	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for SIRTA, FR (DBS)		Remote access (the v	Automatic colorimeter measurements for atmospheric boundary layer profiling in an urban environment.
7	ATMO 2nd TNA call	Complete	Sarneck Laboratory BV	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	The Netherlands	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	No	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for ICN, ES (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	Prototype field analyzer application for simultaneous real-time measurements of Organic, Elemental, Black and Brown Carbon fractions using a dual wavelength laser sen- sor. Dual Carbon Analyser with Thermal Optical method (DUCATO)
8	ATMO 2nd TNA call	Complete	Aerrod d.o.o.	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Slovenia	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	No	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for ICN, ES (DBS)		Combination of Physic	Long term and high-time-resolution validation of advanced total carbon black carbon (TC/BC) method for appointment of primary and secondary carbonaceous aerosols in the western Mediterranean basin (WMB- TC-BC3)
9	ATMO 2nd TNA call	Complete	Palas GmbH	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Germany	Expert scientist	ENG-TECH - Engineering and technology	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for SRO, AT (DBS)		Combination of Physic	Cloud Droplet Analyser (CDA)
10	ATMO 2nd TNA call	Complete	Sensar	Other industrial and/or profit private organization	Sweden	Engineer, Technician	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Technical services (i.e., calibration, i COS-ATC, FR (CJ)		Combination of Physic	Evaluation of a new low-cost, small size multi-channel NDIR sensing platform for GHG concentration measurement with sub-ppm resolution
11	ATMO 2nd TNA call	Complete	OMEL	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	France	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Technical services (i.e., calibration, i SAF -100, ES (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	Characterization Of Aerosols in the submicron ($0.08\mu\text{m}$ to $0.8\mu\text{m}$) (CAUTION)
12	ATMO 2nd TNA call	Complete	OMEL	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	France	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	No	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for SAF -100, ES (DBS)		Remote access (the v	Evaluation of anOid Linear measurements at the nAtellite (Communication challenge)
13	ATMO 3rd TNA call	Complete	TOPWERAG	Other industrial and/or profit private organization	Switzerland	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for QUANC, DE (ASQ)		Physical access (hand)	Testing of a Dual Ionization MS prototype by coupling with an Atmospheric Simulation Chamber
14	ATMO 3rd TNA call	Complete	IB Hyperspectral Devices GmbH	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Germany	Expert scientist	ENV-ECOBIO - Earth and environmental sciences/Geo-biosphere	No	Technical services (i.e., calibration, i CESAAR, NL (DBS)		Combination of Physic	Hyperspectral Assessment of Vertical Atmospheric Resorption of Sun Induced Chlorophyll Fluorescence
15	ATMO 3rd TNA call	Complete	Menapsa Ltd.	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	UK	Other, not specified	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Technical services (i.e., calibration, i CESAAR, NL (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	MedGlobe Tower Verification
16	ATMO 3rd TNA call	Complete	Solis S.A. & University of Namur	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Belgium	Post-graduate	CHEM - Chemistry	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for FAC2-CO, ASQ)		Combination of Physic	Catalytic oxidations for the cleaning of wood stove emissions - a physico-chemical characterization of effluents generated by wood combustion and their maturation in the atmosphere
17	ATMO 3rd TNA call	Complete	GRASP SAS at Facility (WCCAP)	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	France	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for AGORA, ES (DBS), SAF -100, ES (DBS), WCCAP, DE (CJ)		Combination of Physic	Interaction assessment between atmospheric composition and low-cost gas sensor system responses
18	ATMO 3rd TNA call	Complete	Origins earth	Other industrial and/or profit private organization	France	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for USR, CY (DBS)		Combination of Physic	Unmanned Aerial System - Greenhouse Gas Tracker
19	ATMO 3rd TNA call	Complete	Eurac Research	Other industrial and/or profit private organization	Italy	Expert scientist	ENG-TECH - Engineering and technology	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for ATMOS, GR (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	AQUANUS
20	ATMO 5th TNA call	Complete	Sarneck Laboratory BV	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	The Netherlands	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and env	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for ATMOS, GR (DBS), PANSEA, GR (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	DETONATE (Definitive) Test of brown carbon using a dual wavelength laser (d-top)
21	ATMO 5th TNA call	Complete	Code Academy Berlin	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Germany	Post-graduate	ENV-ATMO - Earth and env	Yes	Training services only (i.e., summer) (CAO, IT (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	Training in Instrumentation and Data Analysis for Aerosol at CAO observatory
22	ATMO 7th TNA call	Complete	TOPWERAG	Other industrial and/or profit private organization	Switzerland	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for QUANC, DE (ASQ)		Combination of Physic	Resolving the formation and fate of atmospheric organic aerosol (relics)
23	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Aerrod SAS	SME	Switzerland	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and env	No	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for ATMOS, GR (DBS)		Combination of Physic	Monitoring of Aerosol Chemical Composition with Infrared Spectroscopy
24	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	UM n.l.	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Italy	Other, not specified	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Technical services (i.e., calibration, i WCCAP, DE (CJ)		Physical access (hand)	Evaluation of Dual Beam Absorption Photometer
25	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Luft GmbH	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Germany	Engineer, Technician	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for WOL, PL (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	APD Ground Loop Prevention
26	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Aerrod d.o.o.	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Slovenia	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	No	Technical services (i.e., calibration, i WCCAP, DE (CJ)		Physical access (hand)	Intercomparison of optical absorption measurements using newly developed Aerosolometer AE33 and AE33s with extended wavelength range (3-wavelength)
27	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Aerrod d.o.o.	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Slovenia	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	No	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for ATMOS, GR (DBS)		Combination of Physic	Advanced Carboxonous Aerosol Speciation using the combination of the new Total Carbon Analyser prototype (TCAN) and new 9 wavelength-Aerosolometer (AE33s)
28	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Eventech	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Libya, Lithuania	Other, not specified	ENG-TECH - Engineering and technology	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for WOL, PL (DBS)		Combination of Physic	Eventech Time-Tagger Testing for Laser Applications.
29	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	GRASP SAS	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	France	Expert scientist	MATH - Mathematics	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for WOL, PL (DBS), AMP, PL (DBS)		Combination of Physic	Air Quality in Urban Environment: A Focused Study on Pollution Behavior in Warsaw's Canopy Layer
30	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Dimple Measurement Technologies, LLC	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	USA	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for CO-PD, FR (DBS)		Combination of Physic	Cloud Aerosol Biomass and Dust Interactions Experiment
31	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Picams Inc	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	The Netherlands	Engineer, Technician	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	No	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for CO-PD, FR (DBS)		Combination of Physic	In Situ Measurement of Formaldehyde in a Cloudy Environment using ODS-Picams
32	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	BAOMETRICS SA	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Greece	Sales Manager	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for AMP, PL (DBS)		Combination of Physic	Mobile system solution Development using Scanning Laser system capabilities.
33	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Raymetrics	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Greece	Expert scientist	ENG-TECH - Engineering and technology	Yes	Technical services (i.e., calibration, i USR, CY (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	Remote sensing of Particulate Matter (PM) Concentrations
34	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	European Sensor Systems S.A.	Other industrial and/or profit private organization	Greece	Post-graduate	PHY - Physics, astronomy, astrophysics	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for RADO, RO (DBS)		Combination of Physic	Atmospheric Lidar Data Acquisition Transient Digitizer
35	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Raymetrics	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Greece	Private Sector Employee	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Technical services (i.e., calibration, i RADO, RO (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	Inter comparison campaign
36	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Information missing	TENAM	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	FRANCE	Engineer, Technician	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Technical services (i.e., calibration, i SAF -100, ES (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	Calibration educational nephelometer calibration campaign
37	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Luper Technologies B.V.	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	The Netherlands	Chief Executive Officer	ENG-TECH - Engineering and technology	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for ASQ, DE (ASQ)		Combination of Physic	Atmospheric fate and impact of emissions from airport mixing plume: reactive, oxidant products and SOA formation.
38	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Menapsa Ltd.	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	UK	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	No	Technical services (i.e., calibration, i CESAAR, NL (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	MedGlobe Tower Verification 2
39	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Menapsa Ltd.	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	UK	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	No	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for FMI PAL-SOL, FI (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	IMPACT+
40	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	GRASP Earth	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	France	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	No	Technical services (i.e., calibration, i WCCAP, DE (CJ)		Remote access (the v	High-certification for ACTRIS
41	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Dekati Ltd.	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	FINLAND	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for MAC, UK (ASQ)		Combination of Physic	Unravelling the capability of the DEKATI Oxidation Flow Reactor to explore the toxicity and composition of secondary organic aerosol from indoor emission sources.
42	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Aerrod SAS	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Switzerland	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	No	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for SIRTA, FR (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	enhancing the chemical composition analysis with the AER monitor: leveraging real-time filter spectroscopy for air quality monitoring
43	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Cancelled	IONCON Analytik GmbH	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Austria	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for SIRTA, FR (DBS)		Combination of Physic	Evaluation of the chemical composition of organic aerosol via CHANOFIT-TONAS
44	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	BE Environmental Optics	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	United States of America	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for WOL, PL (DBS)		Remote access (the v	Camera filter evaluation for air quality
45	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Aerrod d.o.o.	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	Slovenia	Expert scientist	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	Yes	Research/Innovation services (i.e. for SIRTA, FR (DBS)		Combination of Physic	Intercomparison of TC-OC method with CAS5 (TCAN-AE33) instruments and the new prototype TCAN-AE33system.
46	ATMO TNA call for private sector	Complete	Observer Instruments	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)	The Netherlands	Post-graduate	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain	No	Technical services (i.e., calibration, i WOPAS, PL (DBS)		Physical access (hand)	Comparison of Sentinel Air Quality System with reference standard station.

Annex 2: Description of the instrument tests performed at the ATC Metrology Laboratory

Figure 1. CH₄ continuous measurement repeatability. First panel: measurements averaged over different time intervals. Second panel: Allan deviation.

The continuous measurement repeatability (CMR) is evaluated with the standard deviation of the continuous measurements of a cylinder over 24 h.

The Allan deviation, which shows the stability as a function of the integration time and informs the optimal integration time, is also calculated and provided in the synthesis report.

Figure 2. Short-term and long-term repeatability for three species, CO₂, CH₄ and CO. First panel: short-term repeatability. Second panel: long-term repeatability

The short-term drift is defined as the peak-to-peak amplitude CMR measurement (previous graph).

The long-term repeatability (LTR) is comparable to the short-term repeatability but on a longer timescale (3 days). In the laboratory, a target gas is measured for 30 min bracketed by around 5 h of wet ambient air over 72 h.

For each measure, only the last 10 min are averaged. The long-term repeatability is then expressed through the standard deviation (SD) of these averaged measures. Typically, several 3-day exercises are performed and the results compared and aggregated at the end of the 1-month duration of the instrument test period. Fig. 2 shows an example of short-term and long-term repeatability. For each species the mean, the SD and the drift are calculated.

For the pressure, the target gas measurements realized during the long-term repeatability test are plotted against the atmospheric pressure over several days to evaluate the correlation between the two.

For the temperature dependence, a temperature-controlled chamber is now used. For each case, the linear regression and the correlation coefficients are calculated.

Figure 4. Linearity test for CO₂. Measured values vs. the assigned values. On the right of the figure: the slope (I1), intercept (I0) and the coefficient of correlation (R²) are indicated. On the lower figure, the residuals, i.e., the difference between the assigned values and the values calculated using the linear equation, are shown.

The linearity of the instrument is also evaluated by measuring six cylinders ranging from low to high concentrations. The residuals from the fit are calculated, and their concentrations along with the correlation coefficient allow us to judge of the linearity of the instrument against the calibration scale. The validity of this test depends strongly on the proper assignation of the concentrations from each calibration cylinder, hence the importance of the link to international scales and the regular recalibrations of the ICOS ATC Metrology Lab calibration cylinders against a “master” set of cylinders provided by the central calibration laboratories.

Figure 5. Cross sensitivity between CO₂ and N₂O.

A cross-sensitivity test is carried out using a tank filled with a high CO₂ concentration which is reduced by passing the gas through an ascarite/magnesium perchlorate trap to evaluate the relationship between CO₂ and N₂O measurements.

Figure 6. Comparison with the reference instrument for CH₄. First panel: dry air vs. dry air. Second panel: wet air corrected for H₂O vs. dry air. On each figure, from top to bottom, the concentrations for both instruments and the difference of the two are plotted, then the water vapor concentrations for both instruments, then the evolution of the target for both instruments and finally a histogram of the distribution of the differences along with statistics.

Comparison with reference instruments: Ambient air measurements from each instrument are compared with other reference instruments maintained by the Metrology Lab. The tested instrument measures wet and dry air and is compared to the reference instrument which measures ambient air dried through a cryogenic water trap. This allows the checking of the factory and Metrology Lab water vapor correction and estimation of the biases. In Fig. 6, the comparison for CH₄ is shown. The H₂O and target gas measurements provide a quality check of the tests. The histogram can help identify outliers if the distribution is strongly not Gaussian. The difference between the wet corrected air and the dry air in the left panel (about 1.2 ppb on average compared to -0.03 ppb for both instruments measuring dry air) is due to the automatic H₂O correction, which is not sufficient to correct all the bias introduced by H₂O.